

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents: Cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide was prepared in the laboratory⁴ and pure mercury(II) nitrate (E. Merck) was used. A citrate buffer of pH 6.5 was prepared from 1g of citric acid (G. R., E. Merck) and sodium hydroxide. A Hilger and Watts H700 Uvispek spectrophotometer was used.

Procedure: Add 1ml of the stock citrate buffer to mercury(II) solution containing 50-450 μg of the metal, dilute to 10 ml, heat to 50° and add 50-60 mg of cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide dissolved in 3-4 ml of ethanol. Adjust the pH to 6.2-8.0 with 2*N* sodium hydroxide solution, cool and extract the complex with two 5 ml portions of isobutyl methyl ketone. Dehydrate the combined extract with sodium sulphate and measure the absorbance at 345 nm against pure solvent within three days.

Results and Discussion

The wave-length of maximum absorbance for the mercury(II) complex was 345 nm where the reagent showed no absorption and Beer's law was valid upto 45 μg of mercury per ml of the solvent.

Fig. 1. Absorbance Curves of Hg(II)-Cyclopentanone-2-Carboxyanilide in isobutylmethyl Ketone.

The complex was extracted in chloroform, benzene and carbon tetrachloride with difficulty. Isobutylmethyl ketone was selected as the extracting solvent due to ease in extraction and the stability of the complex. Approximately 96% of the complex was recovered by one extraction. About 50-60 mg of the reagent was sufficient provided the complex was allowed to form before extraction. Larger amounts of it were required when the extraction was tried with cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide dissolved in the ketone.

Extraction was quantitative above a pH of 6.2. However, mercury(II) (300 μg) could be determined with a relative standard deviation of $\pm 1\%$ in the presence of 0.0 mg of Cu(II), Cd(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Fe(III) or Al(III) provided the pH was adjusted to 7.0-7.5.

Mole-ratio and slope-ratio methods indicated the formation of a mercury(II) bis-complex, the dissociation constant being 5.97×10^{-13} . The Sandell sensitivity was 4.6×10^{-2} μg of mercury(II) per cm^2 while the molar absorptivity at 345 nm was $4400 \pm 4\%$.

References

1. A. K. SARKAR and J. DAS, *Anal. Letters*, 1968, 1, 323.
2. N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 446.
3. N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 33.
4. H. C. BARANY and M. PIANCA, *J. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1947, 1420.

Molecular Interactions—Studies on the Distribution of Aniline between Water and Binary Mixtures of Organic Solvents*

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THE distribution coefficients of aniline between water and binary mixtures of different weight fractions of carbon tetrachloride with benzene or nitrobenzene have been measured at 30° and 40°. The changes in the thermodynamic parameters of free energy, enthalpy and entropy accompanying the transfer of one mole of aniline from the aqueous layer to the organic layer have been calculated.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the present investigation were of Analar quality. The organic liquids were purified by the usual procedures¹. Double-distilled water was employed. The weight percentages of the organic solvents in the binary solvent mixtures were calculated from the known volumes of the two solvents and their density values at 30°.

The method adopted for the determination of the distribution coefficient was the conventional one². The initial concentration of aniline in the aqueous layer was kept at 0.01 *M* in all the experiments. In order to

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bring the systems effectively into equilibrium in each case, the mixture of the organic solvents or the pure organic solvent and the aqueous solution of aniline were kept in the thermostat at the desired temperature and mechanically agitated for about an hour using a mercury-sealed stirrer to prevent evaporation of the solvents. After the two layers separated, each was analysed for its aniline content by the Winkler method².

The free energy change (ΔG°) and the entropy change (ΔS°) at the two temperatures were obtained from the following equations:

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_{dist}$$

$$\Delta S^\circ = \frac{\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ}{T}$$

Results and Discussion

The distribution coefficients reported refer to the following equilibrium :

for which $K_{dist} = \frac{[\text{Aniline in the organic layer}]}{[\text{Aniline in the aqueous layer}]}$

The enthalpy change (ΔH°) of the forward process was calculated using the integrated form of the van't Hoff equation :

$$\frac{d \ln K_{dist}}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H^\circ}{RT^2}$$

The data are given in Table 1 and Table 2.

A survey of the data reveals the following facts :

(i) The transfer of one mole of aniline from the water layer to the nitrobenzene layer is exothermic but is endothermic with the other two solvents, carbon tetrachloride and benzene.

(ii) In all cases ΔG° decreases with increase of temperature.

(iii) The ΔS° values are all positive and do not change with temperature. With different organic solvents, the value increases in the order nitrobenzene < carbon tetrachloride < benzene (4.98, 6.20 and 7.27 e.u. mole⁻¹ respectively).

TABLE—1. DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF ANILINE BETWEEN CARBON TETRACHLORIDE-NITROBENZENE MIXTURES AND WATER, AND RELATED THERMODYNAMIC PROPERTIES

Mole % of carbon tetrachloride	K_{dist}		$-\Delta G^\circ$ Calories mole ⁻¹		ΔH° Calories mole ⁻¹	ΔS° observed e. u. mole ⁻¹		ΔS° Calcd. e. u. mole ⁻¹ 40°	$\Delta \Delta S^\circ$ e. u. mole ⁻¹
	30°	40°	30°	40°		30°	40°		
	100	4.11	4.34	850		910	1030		
70	10.23	10.46	1400	1460	420	6.01	6.01	5.83	+0.18
51	15.22	15.33	1640	1700	140	5.87	5.88	5.60	+0.28
26	19.17	19.01	1780	1830	-155	5.36	5.35	5.30	+0.05
0	21.67	21.29	1850	1900	-340	4.98	4.98	—	—

TABLE—2. DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF ANILINE BETWEEN CARBON TETRACHLORIDE-BENZENE MIXTURES AND WATER, AND RELATED THERMODYNAMIC PROPERTIES.

Mole % of carbon tetrachloride	K_{dist}		$-\Delta G^\circ$ Calories mole ⁻¹		ΔH° Calories mole ⁻¹	ΔS° observed e. u. mole ⁻¹		ΔS° Calcd. e. u. mole ⁻¹ 40°	$\Delta \Delta S^\circ$ e. u. mole ⁻¹
	30°	40°	30°	40°		30°	40°		
	100	4.11	4.34	850		910	1030		
85	5.61	5.88	1040	1100	885	6.35	6.34	6.36	-0.02
48	7.13	7.45	1180	1250	830	6.63	6.64	6.76	-0.12
32	8.14	8.50	1260	1330	815	6.85	6.85	6.93	-0.08
15	9.50	9.90	1355	1425	775	7.03	7.03	7.11	-0.08
0	10.98	11.43	1440	1515	760	7.26	7.27	—	—

NOTES

The more negative ΔG° values at the higher temperature show that the transfer of aniline from water to the organic layer occurs more readily at elevated temperatures.

The positive values of ΔS° indicate that the transfer of aniline from water layer to the organic layer results in a greater randomness in orientation of aniline molecules with the organic solvent molecules. This is obviously due to the highly polar nature of water molecules resulting in a greater order in the intermolecular orientation of polar aniline with them than with non-polar carbon tetrachloride and benzene molecules. Since nitrobenzene is the most polar among the three liquids studied, the ΔS° value is the least with it.

Even though carbon tetrachloride and benzene are both classified as non-polar, the C-Cl bond in the former is more polarisable than the C-H bond in the latter. Hence the possibility of a greater order in the intermolecular orientation of aniline with carbon tetrachloride than with benzene cannot be ruled out. This is confirmed by the greater ΔS° value with benzene (7.27 e.u.) than with carbon tetrachloride (6.20 e.u.).

The $\Delta \Delta S^\circ$ values obtained with mixtures of the two pairs of the organic solvents (Table I and Table 2) show that the carbon tetrachloride-nitrobenzene system exhibits a positive deviation from ideal behaviour (i.e. from the simple mixture rule) while with the carbon-tetrachloride-benzene system the deviation is negative. Further the deviation, positive or negative, appears to be maximum at about 50% composition. This might be due to the greater orderly intermolecular orientation among molecules of carbon tetrachloride and nitrobenzene than among molecules of carbon tetrachloride and benzene. Under such circumstances when aniline molecules get transferred from water to the carbon tetrachloride-nitrobenzene mixture a slightly more randomness of orientation results than there would be if the systems were ideal.

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References

1. WEISSBERGER, "Technique of Organic Chemistry", Vol. VII, Interscience, N. Y., 1955, p. 441.
2. D. BRENNEN and C. F. H. TIPPER, "A Laboratory Manual of Experiments in Physical Chemistry", McGraw Hill Publishing Company Limited, London, 1967, p. 104.

Condensation of *o*-Phenylenediamine with Ethyl Acetoacetate in presence of Polyphosphoric acid.

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ETHYL acetoacetate gives with the diamine under acid condition ethyl β -2-amino-anilinoacronate (m.p. 59°) which undergoes isomerisation to the stable form after eight days (m. p. 85°) in the presence of light; ^{1,2,3} in the present work such a *cis-trans* interconversion could be brought about by treatment with boiling water. Sexton¹ obtained in such a condensation a seven-membered ring compound(I) in neutral boiling Xylene; benzimidazole-2-acetone(II) in alkaline condition and 2-methyl-benzimidazole(III) by heating the crotonate alone at 100°.

He concluded that (I) or (II) might have been formed from the intermediate, acetoacet-*o*-aminoanilide(IV) which he, however, could not isolate.

In the present work such a condensation gave with polyphosphoric acid the above four products but each under different experimental condition. It was however observed in numerous experiments that benzimidazole-2-acetone was obtained at temperatures 120-140° as a stable product and acetoacet-*o*-aminoanilide at 100° under controlled condition; its benzene solution on boiling gave benzimidazole-2-acetone. The variation in the nature of products obtained may be explained on the basis of the exceptional nature of the reagent⁴ and the functional multiplicity of the β -keto ester and diamine.

Experimental

Seven-Membered Ring Compound (I): Freshly prepared polyphosphoric acid (12. ml; 20 g.) was slowly added to an externally ice-cooled mixture of the diamine (5.4g.) and the keto ester (6.8 ml). The reaction mass was heated to 85° and then kept for 24 hours. It was then heated to 150°, treated with ice and neutralised giving a product which was crystallised from alcohol (m.p. 120° - 121°). Its mixed m.p. with the product obtained by the method of Sexton did not show any depression.

Benzimidazole-2-acetone (II): The mixture of the diamine(5.4g.) with the β -ketoester(7 ml.) was mixed with freshly prepared warm PPA (12ml; 20g.), when a vigorous reaction set in with effervescence. It was heated to 150° and kept at this temperature for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. Neutralisation in presence of ice with sodium and ammonium hydroxide solutions precipitated a product. Needles from water (2.2g, m.p. 148°), lit.¹ m.p. 148°.